

Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC): A New Challenge for Oncologists

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Cancer is one among the scariest and lethal diseases in the world, frightening mankind largely for the reason that it is hard to live through it. Since, cancer results from the unrestricted proliferation of specific modified normal human cells, it's neither easy to track it nor to curb it. One of the contemporary solutions to alleviate malignancy comprise drug therapy (chemotherapy) despite the very well-known fact that majority of drugs used for cancer treatment are cytotoxic that work by interfering in some ways with the operation of the cell's DNA.

Breast cancers which do not express oestrogen, progesterone, or HER-2 neu receptors are known as triple negative breast carcinomas (TNBC). In western literature, they have been reported as extremely aggressive with a poor prognosis. However there is paucity of information on breast cancer in India. A number of recent studies have shown that TNBC is not a homogeneous entity at the phenotypic and molecular levels. Clinically, this heterogeneity manifests itself in unpredictable outcomes for patients treated with the same or similar strategies.

Despite poor prognosis, subgroups of TNBC patients have excellent outcomes. There are more chances of recurrence in the first few years after surgery as compared to patients with ER-positive tumors. Thus, the view of TNBC as a homogeneous subtype with uniformly poor prognosis is an over-simplified perception.

Keywords: Triple negative breast cancer, chemotherapy, malignancy.

References:

- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A; Shrivastava, A (2014) Allicin as a potential inducer of apoptosis in cancer cells-I. *National Conference on Recent Updates in Biological Research*, 19.
- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A (2015) Allicin as a potential inducer of apoptosis in cancer cells-II. *National Seminar on Recent Trends in Science & Technology*, 65.
- **Garg, HK;** Choudhary, A (2011) Anticancer & Anti mutagenic Properties of Medicinal Plants. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Biodiversity & Environmental Conservation*, 39.

- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2013) Should labeling be enforced on genetically designed products? *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 20-21.
- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2013) Consternations over genetically designed products. *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 23-24.
- **Garg, HK;** Garg, J (2012) Worldwide Endorsement on Genetically Modified Food. *National Seminar on Science for Shaping the Future of India* organized under the auspices of Indian Science Congress Kolkata & M.P. Council of Science & Technology Bhopal, 68.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A; Choudhary, A (2015) Flavonoids from Lemon & Tea as Effective Inhibitors against Carcinogenesis. *National Seminar on Innovations in Science & Technology for Inclusive Development*, 08.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Andrographolide induced succinate dehydrogenase activity in isolated mitochondrial fractions from different organ of BALB/c mice. *International Organization for Scientific Research - Journal of Pharmacy & Biological Sciences, USA* 6(4) : 43-45.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Evaluation and impact of anti-tuberculosis drug. **International Journal of Scientific Research**, 2(7): 20-21.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Clinical use of andrographolide as a potential drug against vole tuberculosis. **International Journal of Pure & Applied Zoology, USA** 1(3) 223-226.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Allicin as a potent antibiotic against *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and *H. pylori*. **Indian Journal of Applied & Pure Biology** 28 (2) : 213-215.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Effect of *Andrographis paniculata* on *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* species. *Agro-Summit 2013: Changing Scenario of Agriculture in Madhya Pradesh: Prospects & Challenges*. 171/13.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Allicin as a potent antibiotic against dermal infections. *International Conference on Recent Trends in Applied Sciences with Engineering Applications (SCLS1.7)* 57.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2013) Effect of Stress on Glucose Metabolism. *National Seminar on Stress & Health Management*, 40.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2012) Anticancer drugs: Difficulties in development and usages. *National Seminar on Human Papilloma Virus and Control of Cervical Cancer-Current Scenario* (PP-8) 37.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2012) Evaluation and impact of anti-tuberculosis drug lines against an MDR - *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates *National Seminar on Environmental Conservation & Management*, 12.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A; Kalesharia, N (2011) Role of Genetic Research for Identification and Treatment of Cancer. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Research & Analysis for Sustainable Development*, 57.
- **Garg, HK;** Shrivastava, A (2011) Growth inhibition of *E.coli*, *P.vulgaris* and *H. pylori* by Acillin. *National Seminar On Emerging Trends In Biodiversity & Environmental Conservation*, 29.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2015) Allicin as a dermal antibiotic against microbial infections. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 4(12) 1052-1056.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2014) Cytotoxic Potential of Andrographolide against Human Lung Adenocarcinoma Cell Lines - A 549. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, Newzeland* 4(5): 9345-9348.

- Shrivastava, A; **Garg, HK** (2014) Effect of Andrographolide on Proliferation of Mycobacterium canetti. *International Journal for Pharmaceutical Research Scholars* 3(1): 410-413.
- Shrivastava, A; **Garg, HK** (2013) Application of Nano-technology and Biocomputation for treatment of cancer. **The Pharma Innovation Journal, Ukraine** 2(6) : 63-66.
- Shrivastava, A; **Garg, HK** (2013) Cytotoxic Potential of Andrographolide against Bovine Tuberculosis. International Organization for Scientific Research - **Journal of Pharmacy & Biological Sciences, USA** 8(5) : 01-04.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2013) Mycobacterial lipid degrading enzymes as novel drug target against tuberculosis. *National Conference on Innovative & Emerging Trends in Information Technology*. 37.
- Shrivastava, A.; **Garg, HK** (2013) Computer abetted drug design for handling tuberculosis. *National Seminar on Computer Assisted Drug Designing for Green Chemistry*, 21-22.
- Shrivastava, A.; Choudhary, A; **Garg, HK** (2014) Genotoxicity in Pesticide Workers. *National Seminar on Environment Conservation and Sustainable Development: Policies for Safe Future*. 05.